

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ASPECTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DISTANCE LEARNING INTO EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF MEDICAL HIGHER INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

In the statistics, the structure of distance navigation is the only one of the forms of uninterrupted medical education at the graduate school. With permissions ϵ , access control to materials of primary courses, that ability to control knowledge of student.

The National Strategy for Education Development in Ukraine states that informatization of vocational education, formation, and implementation of information educational environment, development of pedagogical software, creation of distance educational systems, and access to world information resources are important conditions for its modernization.

Keywords: medical higher institutions, educational process, advantages of the distance learning, disadvantages of the distance learning.

Introduction.

An alternative form of acquiring knowledge in medicine is distance learning, which is becoming more widespread especially today. It is a new organization of the educational process based on the usage of the best traditional teaching methods and new information and telecommunication technologies [1, 2].

Distance learning is a form of organization of the educational process and pedagogical technology, the basis of which is the managed independent work of students and the wide application of modern information and communication technologies in teaching. The main purpose of distance learning of students is the education of a person who has the desire and ability to communicate, learn, and self-educate [3]. This is a form of education based on the use of information transmission media (information and communication networks, television, mail, radio) and teaching methods that depend on the technical environment of information exchange [2].

Distance learning involves the following means: providing educational material to the student; student performance monitoring; student consultations by the program-teacher; interactive cooperation between teacher and student; the ability to quickly add new information to the course, error correction.

Aim. To analyse the modern state of the distance learning technology in conditions of long period of quarantine and war.

Results and discussions.

Distance learning is also defined as "the technology of acquiring knowledge through telecommunications when the interaction of the learner and the teacher takes place at a distance". In distance learning, the role and requirements for teachers are changing. Teachers of distance courses must have universal training: to have modern pedagogical and information technologies, to be psychologically ready to work with students in a new educational and cognitive environment. And students feel an integral part of the team, which increases motivation to learn. Teachers must have methods of creating and maintaining a learning environment, develop strategies for this interaction between participants in the learning process, increase creative activity, and their own skills [4].

In the West, this form has been used for a long time and is widely popular with students because of its economic performance and educational efficiency. Distance learning is also called "lifelong learning". Due to the need to improve skills or expand the scope of activities, many need to quickly and efficiently acquire new knowledge and skills. It is then that distance learning can become the optimal form. It enables people to obtain a proper education without spending much time [3].

In Ukraine, the provisions on distance learning are regulated by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated September 23, 2003, which approved

the "Program for the Development of the Distance Learning System", which is part of the education system of Ukraine with a regulatory and legal organizational structure, personnel, system engineering, technical and financial support, that implements distance learning of higher and postgraduate self-education. According to the program, distance learning is an individualized process of assimilation of knowledge, abilities, skills, and methods of cognitive activity, which takes place through the mediated interaction of remote participants in a specialized environment created on the basis of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies [5-6].

The advantages of distance learning are convincing. First, training takes place according to the "24 x 7" or "anywhere-anytime" scheme: the student can choose the time and place of training himself (at home, at work, etc.). Secondly, an individual approach to everyone. A remote teacher acts more as an assistant, mentor, advisor, that is why he is called a tutor abroad. In addition to individual work, distance learning systems often organize work in small groups. Working in groups can have a significant impact on learning the learning material. Thirdly, - limited duration with high quality of education. The most popular has become training under programs that have a clear direction: those who study receive only the knowledge and skills that are necessary for the performance of their work. Usually, tutors have extensive experience in practical work in their field, while the focus in the learning process is on practical application of knowledge and consideration of real examples [6].

According to some authors, the ability to reflect and search for new knowledge occupies a special place in distance education. The ability to reflect is the most important component of the educational process and can be achieved by using a special system of active learning methods and means of interaction. Interactivity in distance education is considered as the interaction of the participants of the educational process, on the one hand, and as a didactic property of the used educational tools. Since the main emphasis in distance learning is on the independent cognitive activity of students individually or in small groups, preference is given to interactive feedback [2, 3].

At the same time, we will highlight such significant disadvantages of distance learning as: - lack of direct contact between student and teacher, as well as interaction between students; - the main method of communication in distance courses remains text, therefore, the opportunity to use non-verbal contact methods is missed; - uneven distribution of the educational load, which occurs when the students' ability to study independently is insufficiently developed (practice shows that the student often leaves a significant part of the course for the very last moment). The most common web resources for distance learning are: the Moodle platform (<https://moodle.org/>) – a free open distance learning management system. chose higher educational institutions. In 2019, Moodle is used by 229 countries around the world, including Ukraine (in Ukrainian), free of charge. The Google Classroom platform (<https://classroom.google.com>) is a service that connects

Google Docs, Google Drive, and Gmail, and allows you to organize online learning using video, text, and graphic information. Zoom (zoom.us/download) – a service for conducting video conferences and online meetings. ClassDojo (<https://www.classdojo.com/uk-ua/signup/>) is a simple tool for evaluating class work in real time. Classtime (<https://www.classstime.com/uk/>) is a platform for creating interactive educational applications that allows you to conduct analytics of the educational process and implement individual approach strategies [5, 6].

We, the teachers of the clinical discipline, are more concerned not with the quality of the distance learning tools, but with the psychological-pedagogical and methodical support of the learning and teaching processes, in particular the acquisition of practical skills. We still have insufficient experience of distance learning, but we can already state that the motivation for independent educational activities of education seekers is only being formed. This encourages teachers to review and transform methodical materials and materials that accompany the educational process. Therefore, nowadays the main "figures" of distance education have become teachers, who act as "architects" and "designers" of informatization and "digitization" of educational materials and visual aids. During distance education, the main activity of the teacher was transformed: from the transfer of educational information to teaching students to work independently with any resources to master the discipline. Therefore, the effectiveness of educational activities largely depends on the level of organizational and cognitive independence of the students of education and the means of individual support for their educational activities [4]. In the distance education system, the educational process includes the transmission (transfer) of knowledge, which is carried out by various teachers who specialize in this specific field; the organization of cognitive activity and control of all educational courses, which is controlled by the head of the department or the head teacher. Thus, distance learning can be imagined as a special model of setting and solving educational tasks or as a specific humanitarian technology for realizing the interests of educational subjects. Educational culture, actualizing e-learning, involves further research in the fields of philosophy and methodology of distance learning, take into account modern information and communication technologies, approaches to the educational system itself: a model of the virtual (distance) educational process; participants of the virtual (distance) educational process: virtual student, virtual teacher. But how to preserve and develop human nature in the virtual educational space? It is necessary for virtual reality to become increasingly humanistic. According to practitioners, in the distance learning process it is advisable to rely on reflection - a sensory-experienced process of awareness by the subject of education of his activity. With the help of reflection, at least three sides of the activity of distance learning subjects are understood: practical (What was done? What is the main result?); technological (In what way? Stages, activity algorithms, etc.); worldview (Why am I doing this? Does the obtained result correspond to the set goals? Who am

I in this work, process? What changes have happened to me or may happen? etc.). Reflection is especially relevant in the conditions of distance learning, since there is no real communication with the teacher, it is necessary to perform most of the educational tasks in the mode of self-testing [7]. In fact, by answering the above questions, the students of education enter the mode of self-education. As you can see, in distance learning, the global subject of the virtual learning process is the Internet community, which, in turn, must be managed. Therefore, humanitarian pedagogical technology is needed, which would manage distance education - a new educational practice. The issue of mastery of practical skills by dental students remains open. For now, this is possible in phantom classes and simulation centers. And what about distance education? Maybe specialized IT specialists will create a virtual model for students to learn practical skills in local anesthesia, how to hold and use surgical instruments? There are still several issues that should be considered and brought up for discussion in the dental community [8]. Therefore, there is something to work on, there is a desire, we think that we will find both opportunities and like-minded people.

Conclusions. Thus, given the guidelines for the development of education in Ukraine, the benefits of distance learning, possible obstacles in the organization and implementation of such an educational process, we can conclude that distance learning in schools is not just a fashion cry of the XXI century, and need and inevitability. To do this, it is necessary to provide information and methodological educational base and train highly qualified specialists to implement the distance learning process. Today, distance education is developing, improving and covering different groups of the population, because modern learning is characterized by a paradigm – to learn throughout life,

which in turn leads to a new leap in education in health care in many countries and in Ukraine in particular.

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